

ENER GIZE

SUPPORTING THE CLEAN ENERGY
TRANSITION OF EUROPEAN BUSINESSES

Specifications list mapping report for setting up an Urban Industrial Energy Community (IREC)

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Executive Summary

The **ENERGIZE project**, co-funded by the European Commission under the LIFE Clean Energy Transition program, aims to accelerate the clean energy transition in European industrial zones. ENERGIZE seeks to reduce CO₂ emissions, enhance energy efficiency, and create sustainable skills and job opportunities by fostering collaborative energy models.

As part of these efforts, ENERGIZE is conducting a comprehensive benchmarking of past and ongoing initiatives related to energy efficiency (EE), industrial energy cooperation, circularity, and industrial ecology. The project also examines the legal and socio-economic requirements necessary to develop sustainable business models in these contexts. This analysis aims to extract key lessons from existing experiences and identify areas for improvement, ultimately **defining the technical, regulatory, and socio-economic conditions needed to establish thriving urban eco-industrial energy communities**.

Within this framework, **Task 2.3: Review of existing energy community success case studies and specifications for setting up an urban-industrial energy community** includes the definition of a comprehensive list of specifications for establishing urban-industrial energy communities (IRECs). These specifications address key dimensions such as **energy generation and distribution, business model templates, and sustainability objectives**, drawing on findings from Deliverables D2.1, D2.2, and D2.3:

- **D2.1-Review of Regional Urban - Industrial Park (Energy Cooperation) Initiatives:** analysed 125 (eco-)industrial park initiatives across Europe and beyond, highlighting successful collaboration and energy cooperation models.
- **D2.2-Review report for ENERGIZE+ business models' creation:** reviewed legal frameworks and financing mechanisms to identify business models suited to industrial energy communities.
- **D2.3-Review of existing energy communities:** examined over 60 energy communities and detailed best practices related to governance, engagement, and financial sustainability.

This report, **D2.4 – Specifications List Mapping Report for Setting Up an Urban-Industrial Energy Community**, presents a user-friendly overview of the key specifications required to establish such communities. The report begins with a **conceptual framework** that clarifies essential terms, such as *urban eco-industrial parks, energy cooperation models, citizen energy communities, and renewable energy communities*, and explains the differences between them. A detailed **methodological approach** is then outlined to support the real-world application of these specifications.

The core of the report is a structured **mind mapping exercise**, which organises information into three main **development phases** (Initial Definition, Setup and Development, and Consolidation and Growth) and three key **thematic areas**:

- **Governance and Participation**
- **Financing and Legal Aspects**
- **Energy and Technical Projects**

For each area and phase, the report identifies **critical success factors**, the **main tasks** required for implementation, and the **key stakeholders** to be involved. This mind map offers a practical, visual guide

for project developers, public authorities, and other stakeholders interested in initiating or supporting IREC models.

Additionally, a **preliminary business model canvas** further builds on the insights from D2.2, refining the core components needed to develop viable and scalable IRECs.

Together, these foundations provide an actionable and replicable framework that will inform the development of **ENERGIZE services** and the project's **Digital Hub**, supporting the creation of resilient, community-based energy models tailored to industrial zones.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION	ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
BM	Business Model	e.g.	For Example
BMC	Business Model Canvas	EIP	Eco-Industrial Park
CBA	Cost-benefit analysis	ESCO	Energy Service Company
CE	Circular Economy	EU	European Union
CECs	Citizen Energy Communities	GHG	Greenhouse Gas
CEP	Clean Energy Package for all Europeans	ICA	International Cooperative Alliance
CHP	Combined Heat and Power	IREC	Industrial renewable Energy Community
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide	RECs	Renewable Energy Communities
DSO	Distribution system operator	RED	Renewable Energy Directive
ECs	Energy Communities	RES	Renewable Energy Sources
EE	Energy Efficiency	SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive	TSO	Transmission system operator
		WP	Work Package

1 Introduction: objectives and definitions

The transition to a low-carbon economy calls for innovative, collaborative, and scalable approaches to energy management, particularly in industrial zones where energy demand and decarbonisation potential are both high. Within this context, **Urban-Industrial Renewable Energy Communities (IRECs)** represent a promising model to integrate clean energy solutions, industrial symbiosis, and community engagement into cohesive frameworks that benefit both local economies and the environment.

This report, developed as part of the ENERGIZE project, builds on the insights of more than 185 initiatives analysed in previous deliverables (D2.1, D2.2, and D2.3). It aims to consolidate this knowledge into a practical and comprehensive **list of specifications** that can guide stakeholders in setting up successful IRECs. By identifying the conditions, processes, and key actors involved across different phases of development, the report supports the replication and scalability of IREC models across Europe.

Specifically, the report pursues the following objectives:

1. **To define a clear and actionable set of specifications** for establishing Urban-Industrial Renewable Energy Communities (IRECs), synthesizing findings from ENERGIZE’s prior research.
2. **To structure the development process** of IRECs across three key phases—Initial Definition, Set-up and Development, and Consolidation and Growth—and three thematic areas: Governance and Participation, Financing and Legal Aspects, and Energy and Technical Projects.
3. **To inform the design of ENERGIZE+ services and the Digital Hub** by offering a replicable framework that supports the implementation of resilient, community-based energy models in industrial contexts.

1.1 Definitions and theoretical concepts

Given **ENERGIZE**'s focus on promoting sustainable energy practices in industrial zones, it is crucial to establish a clear foundational framework. This requires precise definitions of the main and basic concepts that will provide the necessary context for understanding the policies and strategies explored in later sections.

1.1.1 (Urban eco-) Industrial parks [1]

Following the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), “[a]n industrial park is a tract of land developed and subdivided into plots according to a comprehensive plan with the provision of roads, transportation and public utilities, sometimes also with common facilities, for use by a group of manufacturers” [2] **Urban industrial parks aim to balance the needs of industrial growth with urban development**, enhancing economic competitiveness while minimizing impacts on the surrounding urban environment [3] [. These parks are specialized areas within cities designed to accommodate **clusters of industrial activities and businesses**. They are planned to integrate urban and industrial functions,

providing space for manufacturing, logistics, and related services, while ensuring the availability of infrastructure such as transportation and utilities. These parks aim to stimulate economic growth, support job creation and attract investment by providing companies with access to resources and proximity to markets [3] [4] A key feature of these parks is their ability to promote “urban-industrial integration”, which links industrial activity with urban development. This integration supports better planning for housing, transportation, and services for workers, and aims to reduce the disconnection between residential and industrial areas [3].

In recent years, there has been a trend towards the development of “eco-industrial parks” (EIP), which emphasize sustainability by focusing on resource efficiency, waste reduction, and environmental management. These parks are designed to foster symbiotic relationships between companies, allowing them to share resources and minimize environmental impact, creating a model for sustainable industrial growth [5] [6] [7] [8]

However, individual companies still face technical and financial barriers to replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy sources, which hinders the installation of renewable energy. The EIP concept therefore aims to create synergies between companies, enabling them to use natural and economic resources together and efficiently, while promoting the use of renewable energy sources in industry. Synergies between EIPs and adjacent urban areas can lead to the development of optimized energy production facilities, so that the surplus energy is available to meet part of the energy needs of the surrounding cities [5] Urban EIPs exhibit facets of industrial ecology, circular economy, and industrial symbiosis, and are generally compatible with the concept of energy cooperation. In summary, the following conclusion can be drawn:

Figure 1-1 Urban eco-industrial parks in the context of industrial ecology, industrial symbiosis, energy cooperations and circularity. Source: Own compilation.

Urban eco-industrial parks can act as platforms for implementing **industrial ecology** by facilitating **industrial symbiosis** and promoting **energy cooperation**, which together contribute to achieving **circularity** and are integrated into urban settings.

Through collaboration and resource sharing, businesses in these parks can reduce waste, optimize resource use, and improve energy efficiency, aligning with the principles of a circular economy. These interconnections foster more sustainable, resilient, and economically efficient (industrial) environments and balance the needs of industrial growth with urban development.

1.1.2 Energy Cooperation [1]

Energy cooperation is defined as a **collaborative approach to sustainable energy solutions, encompassing the production, procurement and consumption of energy among multiple stakeholders**. This cooperation aims to optimize energy demand and improve sustainability by pooling resources and fostering partnerships. Examples include shared energy production plants, district heating systems and waste heat recovery within industrial parks or between industrial companies and surrounding communities.

A key aspect of energy cooperation is its alignment with **industrial symbiosis**, which focuses on resource exchange among companies. Energy cooperation serves as a subset of this concept, specifically targeting energy-related activities such as joint procurement, shared infrastructure and knowledge exchange. These collaborations often occur in geographically localized settings, involving stakeholders from various sectors, including SMEs, local authorities and utility providers.

Trust and robust communication are critical to the success of energy cooperation. Effective coordination ensures optimized resource use, enhanced energy efficiency and shared value creation, yielding both environmental and financial benefits. However, **energy cooperation remains a relatively rare practice**, with challenges such as heterogeneous project characteristics, varying energy needs and differing levels of trust between stakeholders.

1.1.3 Energy Community (ECs) [9]

Following the definitions provided by the European Commission [10] and the RESCoop initiative [11] Energy Communities (ECs) provide a structured framework for individuals, businesses, and local entities to engage in collaborative energy-related activities, **characterized by open and democratic participation and governance**. Their fundamental objective centers on **delivering services and benefits to their members and the broader local community, rather than prioritizing financial profit maximization**. Recognized as a distinct type of market actor within the Clean Energy Package (CEP), ECs embody a social innovation approach, fostering decentralized, citizen-led energy initiatives that actively contribute to the clean energy transition.

ECs serve as **catalysts for collective and citizen-driven energy actions**, playing a pivotal role in supporting the clean energy transition. They contribute to increased public acceptance of RES projects and facilitate

the attraction of private investments essential for driving the transition. Moreover, **ECs empower citizens to assume a leading role in local energy transitions**, enabling them to directly benefit from enhanced energy efficiency, reduced energy expenditures, mitigation of energy poverty, and expanded local green job opportunities.

By operating as a cohesive unit, ECs gain access to a wider range of energy markets, participating on a level playing field with other market actors. This collective strength enhances their ability to effectively compete and leverage economies of scale. Under EU law, ECs enjoy considerable flexibility in their legal constitution, with options encompassing various legal entities such as associations, cooperatives, partnerships, non-profit organizations, and limited liability companies. (source: European Commission) **This adaptability allows ECs to tailor their organizational structure to the specific needs and circumstances of their local context.**

In summary, **ECs represent a significant evolution in energy systems, promoting community-based, participatory models that prioritize social, environmental, and economic well-being alongside energy production and consumption.** By empowering citizens and fostering collaborative action, ECs contribute significantly to the realization of a sustainable, resilient, and inclusive energy future.

1.1.4 Citizen Energy Community (CECs) [9]

Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) are legally defined under the Internal Market for Electricity Directive of the European Commission (IMED) [12]. The IMED establishes common rules for the generation, transmission, distribution, energy storage and supply of electricity, together with consumer protection provisions, with a view to creating truly integrated competitive, consumer-centred, flexible, fair and transparent electricity markets in the Union. Following this definition, CECs are legal entities that:

- Are based on **voluntary and open participation**, and is **effectively controlled by members or shareholders** that are natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises;
- Have for its primary purpose to **provide environmental, economic or social community benefits** to its members or shareholders or to the local areas where it operates rather than to generate financial profits;
- And **may engage in generation**, including from RES, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services to its members or shareholders.

1.1.5 Renewable Energy Community (RECs) [9]

Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) are legally defined under the Renewable Energy Directive (REDII) of the European Commission [13]. The REDII *promotes the use of energy from renewable sources to facilitate the energy transition*, supporting cooperation between EU countries towards this goal. Following this definition, REC are legal entities that:

- Are based (in accordance with the applicable national law) on **open and voluntary participation**, is autonomous, and is **effectively controlled by shareholders** or members that **are located in the proximity** of the renewable energy projects that are owned and developed by that legal entity;
- The shareholders or members of which are **natural persons, SMEs or local authorities**, including municipalities;
- The primary purpose is to provide **environmental, economic or social community benefits** for its shareholders or members or for the local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits.

1.1.6 Key differences between CECs and RECs [9]

While CECs, RECs and energy cooperation share a cooperative and community-driven ethos, and prioritize environmental, economic and social benefits over financial profits, they differ in several key ways [14], in particular regarding:

- **Policy support:** Energy cooperation lacks a formal legal structure within European energy policies, whereas energy communities, such as RECs and CECs, are supported by specific regulations under the EU's Clean Energy Package and other policies.
- **Membership and governance:** requirements regarding the autonomy of RECs and the involvement of citizens as decision-makers in RECs are more rigorous compared to CECs.
- **Geographical scope:** RECs will exhibit a **more localized dimension**, with controlling authority delegated to members in proximity to installations, whereas CECs will possibly also operate on a national scale, allowing effective control to occur without the necessity for proximity to installations.
- **Energy Sources:** RECs will **exclusively utilize technology for energy production from renewable sources**, encompassing electricity, gas and heat. In contrast, CECs have the flexibility to employ both fossil-fuel and renewable-based technologies, but solely for electricity production.
- **Regulatory Framework:** RECs, as predominantly non-professional entities, benefit from a comparatively more developed regulatory framework.

Despite their differences, both RECs and CECs aim to facilitate the clean energy transition through collective energy production, distribution and consumption. These models represent structured, regulated approaches to energy collaboration, in contrast to the broader and less formalized scope of energy cooperation. By understanding these distinctions, stakeholders in urban-industrial parks can better identify opportunities to adopt cooperative or community-based energy models that align with their specific needs and contexts.

For further insights into the implementation of CECs and RECs, the Energy Community Secretariat's *Policy Guidelines on the Concepts of Energy Communities* [15] provides a comprehensive analysis of their similarities and differences.

1.1.7 Cooperatives [9]

A cooperative is defined by the International Cooperative Alliance (ICA) as an “*autonomous association of individuals who voluntarily come together to fulfil shared economic, social, and cultural needs through a jointly owned and democratically controlled enterprise*” [16]. Rooted in principles of collective decision-making and member-driven governance, cooperatives prioritize community benefit over profit maximization.

As **people-centered enterprises**, they are owned, controlled and run by and for their members to realise their common economic, social, and cultural needs and aspirations, and they operate on the principle of *one member, one vote*, ensuring equal participation in decision-making regardless of its financial contribution.

As **value-driven enterprises**, cooperatives prioritize cooperation, fairness and sustainability over profit maximization, and align with [internationally agreed principles](#) established by the ICA in 1995. These principles include [17]

- **Voluntary and open membership** – Accessible to all who share the cooperative’s goals.
- **Democratic member control** – Managed by members through equal voting rights.
- **Economic participation** – Members contribute equitably and control the financial structure.
- **Autonomy and independence** – Self-governed and free from external control.
- **Education, training, and information** – Committed to continuous learning and skill development.
- **Cooperation among cooperatives** – Encouraging collaboration to strengthen the movement.
- **Concern for the community** – Working towards sustainable social and economic development.

Their legal framework varies across Europe, with different regulatory models depending on the country. Despite these legal differences, **cooperatives remain a prevalent model for citizen-led energy initiatives in Europe**, particularly for energy communities.

As an example of the differences, a study performed in 2012 [18] by EURICSE classified them as follows:

- No specific cooperative law (e.g. Denmark)
- Independent cooperative law (e.g. Austria, Germany)
- Cooperative regulation in the commercial code (e.g. Czech Republic, Slovakia)
- Cooperative regulation in the company law (e.g. Luxembourg) or in the companies’ code (e.g. Belgium)
- Cooperative regulation in the civil code (e.g. Italy, the Netherlands)
- Cooperative regulation in the code of cooperatives (e.g. Portugal)

2 Methodology

This deliverable includes the main results and key findings from the deliverables D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3 of WP2, which provided an overview of the previous and existing initiatives in the area of energy, communities in Industrial zones and legal and socio-economical requirements for business models related. This report collected all the data from the previous deliverables and present this in a more clear and schematic way, that helps to identify the success factors when setting up and Industrial Renewable Energy Community (IREC).

2.1 D2.1 Review of Regional Urban - Industrial Park (Energy Cooperation) Initiatives summary

The deliverable D2.1 [1] was produced within Task 2.1, which focused on gathering and reviewing existing and past initiatives related to (urban) eco-industrial parks, with a specific emphasis on the participation, collaboration and energy cooperation between businesses within these parks and their surrounding areas. The aim was to analyse how such initiatives have facilitated collaboration, energy sharing, or other forms of cooperative engagement among industrial entities and their neighbouring communities on European and global scale. This review provided valuable insights into best practices and potential opportunities for enhancing energy efficiency and (renewable) energy cooperation in similar settings for ENERGIZE.

The outcomes of Task 2.1 were presented in deliverable D2.1. It included an introductory overview of the theory and concepts of (urban eco-) industrial parks, industrial symbiosis, industrial ecology, circularity and energy cooperation. There were also defined key parameters which allowed the collection of concrete initiatives providing a comprehensive overview of (urban eco-) industrial park initiatives. The data collection was also available in the accompanying Excel file *Data Collection D.2.1* with detailed information on the analysed industry park initiatives. Further, the collected data and information were analysed, and key findings were derived.

2.2 D2.2: Review report for ENERGIZE+ business models' creation summary

Deliverable D2.2 [19] was part of the Task 2.2, having the ambition of providing the necessary instruments for performing an analysis of the ENERGIZE application in industrial sector in the target countries, and then identifying the most robust and replicable Business Models (BMs).

The overall approach of the study was founded on strong understanding of the State of the Art of the sector of intervention. The study was performed by (i) reviewing official report, documents, literature and (ii) involving stakeholders to gather updated information. Defining benchmarks was approached not only by studying the market in its general terms (macroeconomics, regulation, sizing, financing, etc.), but focusing on adopted business models, which were chosen as the key tool for identifying barriers and opportunities in the reference market.

The review of the legal and regulatory framework and financial mechanisms highlighted both strengths and gaps within the European context and individual Member States. While current regulations and incentives are strongly oriented towards supporting the energy transition, they often favour small-scale configurations and leave room for improvement in supporting large-scale initiatives within industrial parks.

Was found that greater regulatory harmonisation across European countries could facilitate the adoption of cooperative models on a larger scale, reducing disparities in access to incentives and simplifying administrative requirements. In addition, targeted financial instruments tailored to the specific needs of industrial parks could accelerate the energy transition by promoting solutions such as energy storage and shared resource management.

The **analysis of financing mechanisms** across the European Union revealed barriers and opportunities in supporting the development of IRECs. While funding programs are all fully aligned with the EU's goals for decarbonization and energy transition, their accessibility, scope, and implementation vary significantly, reflecting differences in regional priorities, economic contexts, and financial strategies.

Despite existing barriers, several opportunities could enhance the effectiveness of financing mechanisms for renewable energy projects and IRECs. The most relevant found were (1) Alternative financing mechanisms like crowdlending and equity crowdfunding, (2) Tailored financial programs to be set starting on ongoing ones to support high-power capacity IRECs, (3) European-Level Funding Programs focused on green transitions and regional development (4) Capacity-building initiatives to enhance IREC groups to better leverage available resources.

Even if strong opportunities were identified in all the four target countries, (Italy, Spain, Austria and Czech Republic), several barriers were found to be still persistent at both EU and country level, such as (1) main focus on small-scale projects only, (2) administrative complexity, which discourages participation, particularly for SMEs and energy communities, (3) regional and economic disparities, especially in less economically developed regions, (4) investment risks due to regulatory changes, high initial costs and long payback periods, (5) limited crowdfunding options, (6) weak EU-level coordination, which is desired to harmonize strategies across Member States, reducing regional disparities and enhancing the overall efficiency of funding mechanisms.

At the time of publishing the results of deliverable D2.2 report, there was still missing the analysis of the stakeholders involved in all the project pilots, their needs and demands, which was due for a later date. Therefore, D2.2 had only a first draft approach on business model's creation. **A more detailed and exhaustive analysis and identification of business models is presented** in section [3](#) of this present document.

2.3 D2.3 – Review of existing energy community's summary

This report [9] explored the key success factors in the development of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) across Europe.

The research employed a mixed-methods approach, combining a comprehensive literature review with an analysis of over 60 successful Energy Community (EC) initiatives and an in-depth examination of ten exemplary RECs. The analysis focused specifically on RECs due to their strong emphasis on community ownership, democratic governance, and renewable energy sources.

Key insights from the research revealed that successful RECs prioritize active community engagement, tailoring projects to local needs and fostering a sense of shared ownership. Collaboration with local authorities is crucial for accessing resources and navigating legal frameworks, while a strategic approach that starts with smaller projects and gradually expands helps build trust and experience. RECs thrive when they embrace diverse renewable energy technologies and consider projects beyond just generation, such as energy storage and grid operation. Furthermore, strong governance with clear rules, a shared vision, and a dedicated leadership team ensures effective decision-making and community empowerment. Finally, financial sustainability relies on diversifying funding sources, including crowdfunding, member contributions, and public funding opportunities.

The analysis also highlighted the importance of understanding the community's unique context and needs, minimizing environmental impact, embracing innovation and circularity principles, and providing complementary services that enhance community well-being. In conclusion, it was found that establishing successful RECs requires a holistic approach that considers governance, financing, technical aspects, and, most importantly, community engagement.

3 Business models

This section provides a **preliminary assessment of potential business models** (BMs) relevant to the ENERGIZE framework. The analysis at this stage aims to identify broad categories of models applicable to IRECs and their preliminary BM canvas. The stakeholder consultation will confirm or change the assessment with real data and workshops. This iterative approach ensures that the final models are **robust, context-specific, and aligned with stakeholder priorities**. This phased approach ensures that the BMs are not only **theoretically sound** but also **practically implementable**, addressing the unique requirements of pilot local stakeholders.

Different business models have been assessed:

- **BM1** – IREC owned by industrial estate members. Companies within an industrial estate collectively own and manage renewable energy assets and energy efficiency projects, sharing costs, benefits and responsibilities.
- **BM2** – IREC owned by ESCOs. Energy Service Companies finance and implement energy efficiency upgrades and renewable energy systems, recovering costs through savings.
- **BM3** – IREC owned by RECs. Residents, local entities and public actors actively participate to finance, manage and share energy assets and electricity production between members.
- **BM4** – IREC for flexibility services. Technological innovation with remote sensor enables industrial loads balancing and scheduling, offering value to local DSOs and TSOs, allowing IRECs to become pivotal actors in the energy sector.
- **BM5** - IREC mixed ownership and multi-services. Hybrid model in which industries, service providers and public actors jointly develop and operate renewable energy assets, managed through a multi-layered governance structure.

Each model is briefly described below, outlining its core function, how it works, and potential benefits for its members participating in ENERGIZE project. While this analysis identifies key characteristics and potential applications, it represents an initial step.

Stakeholder consultation is a crucial process for engaging interested parties in decision-making and defines the most suitable legal form based on each member state. ENERGIZE could understand which governance and business legal models are available for each pilot country. Municipal or citizens' participation in such processes can be limited due to factors like higher technical involvement or resource constraints. ESCOs could play a vital role in energy-related projects, and their collaboration with different governance frameworks for IREC can be instrumental in achieving shared objectives. Ultimately, a nation's specific rules and regulations significantly influence stakeholder engagement, organizational structures, and the impact of private developers and public associations.

3.1 BM1 – IREC owned by industrial estate members

Table 3-1 BM1 description

BM1 in a nutshell
<p>Each member of the IREC invests in a renewable plant, that is installed within its own industrial parks that leads to (i) energy efficiency with self-consumption and carbon emission minimization and (ii) enter the energy market for selling excess electricity. The member owns the surface area and technical asset (e.g. renewables plants and energy consumption infrastructure), and it operates and maintains the technological asset with the support of internal staff trained in collective energy management for the IREC. BM1 is suitable for industrial associations or group of medium-large enterprises.</p>
Overview
<p>BM1 fully addresses the challenges of a sustainable economy, the efficiency exploitation of natural resources (solar, wind, water, etc..) and the high demand for a reliable electricity supply for enterprises.</p> <p>It embraces the cooperative approach while balancing the three components, with a special focus on (i) the efficient use of the natural resource (e.g. water, energy, production material) (ii) energy efficiency of industrial production to minimize waste (iii) clean energy generation to reduce carbon emissions from fossil fuels, thus enhancing energy security. This type of model is highly replicable and scalable, making it suitable for different sizes of industrial actors and a large variety of energy patterns.</p> <p>Thus, a suitable financing structure for BM1 could consist of different mechanism such as: (i) grant financing (in form of progress-based grant and technical assistance), (ii) microfinancing for industrial association, (iii) commercial loans for medium-large enterprise and (iv) junior debt.</p>
How it works
<p>BM1 is to implement by an Industrial Park member (either industrial association or a medium-large enterprise) that wants to install a renewable plant on its own facility or available land. Three asset clusters characterize BM1: (i) renewable power generation plants, (ii) systems and personnel for energy management, and (iii) available surfaces. All three asset clusters are owned by the same entity, which is also responsible for their operation within an integrated business model. Technical support for energy management is required to assure the business sustainability. The business objective is to diversify the revenue streams and enable energy sales in the market.</p> <p>Key partners include (i) public financing entities able to support capital costs through de-risking financing mechanisms, (ii) private financing institutions, (iii) technology providers, which can be categorized into renewable technology suppliers and smart meter providers.</p>

Reference project in operation for the BM1

Scientific literature classifies this model such as an “energy cooperative” [20] or “bottom-up model” [21]. BM1 proposes IRECs in terms of general project governance, key stakeholders, and a shared community-based approach.

3.2 BM2 – IREC owned by ESCOs

Table 3-2 BM2 description

BM2 in a nutshell

An ESCo invests in and installs renewable plants within industrial parks, providing comprehensive energy services including audits, building improvements, and energy management. With the support of trained staff, the ESCo owns and operates both temporary surface rights and technical assets (renewable plants and energy consumption equipment). This model fosters a dual community - both physical and interest-based - making it ideal for industrial associations and groups of medium-large enterprise seeking integrated energy solutions with reduced technical burden.

Overview

BM2 fully addresses the financial burden faced by enterprises. Unlike conventional technology vendors or energy consultants, an ESCo can finance energy systems, and its compensation is typically based on the energy savings achieved by its clients.

Several variations of this business model can be leveraged. In addition to developing energy generation systems, community ESCo can offer building retrofits and energy-efficient equipment (e.g. air conditioners and electric water heaters). By offering these services, ESCo guarantees additional energy savings for their clients, securing their revenue streams, as they are compensated based on the actual energy saving achieved.

Thus, a suitable financing structure for BM2 could consist of alternative revenues stream, such as reimbursements schemes or fringe benefits for employees.

How it works

BM2 is implemented by an ESCo that seeks to install a renewable plant on IREC land. Under BM2, revenues generated for industrial park members - such as energy savings - can be shared between the ESCo and its customers in different ways and used to reimburse ESCo of their investments. In some Member-States, ESCo are also exploring combined power and heat solutions.

In all cases, the energy operator supplies the technical know-how in both situations, helping to scale the initiative. Depending on the level of investment and the chosen business model, incentives can

be allocated between the energy operator and the industrial park members.

ESCO payment plans typically include (i) guaranteed savings, the ESCo commits to provide specific energy savings, and (ii) shared savings, which are distributed over a set period according to a pre-established agreement between the ESCo and its clients.

Reference project in operation for the BM2

Relevant examples include “solar-as-a-service” and “heat-as-service”, where community ESCo finance PV systems or heating district infrastructure while managing installation, upstream supply, and maintenance. This BM enables end-users to become prosumers [22] [23] [24] Scientific literature classifies this model such as a “community ESCo” or “energy operator model” [21].

3.3 BM3 – IREC owned by RECs

Table 3-3 BM3 description

BM3 in a nutshell
<p>A REC led by citizens and public entities, invests and installs renewable plants within industrial parks, providing comprehensive energy services including audits, building improvements, waste recovery and energy management. With the support of trained staff, the REC owns and operates the technical assets (renewable plants and energy consumption equipment), enabling energy efficiency through self-consumption and market participation via excess electricity sales. The model fosters a dual community - both physical and interest-based - making it ideal for industrial associations and public administrations seeking integrated energy solutions for their territories.</p>
Overview
<p>BM3 fully addresses the challenge of sustainable territories, optimizing the use of natural resources (solar, wind, water, etc..) and meeting the high demand of reliable electricity supply from enterprises.</p> <p>Prosumer-focused REC are typically local communities established by prosumers, who act as investors, customers, and decision-makers. They collaborate to leverage special financing terms when purchasing assets or buying energy in bulk.</p> <p>Thus, a suitable financing structure for BM3 could consist of different mechanism such as: (i) crowdfunding initiatives (ii) loans (iii) grant for social inclusive projects that could benefit local associations and cooperatives focused on specific initiatives (e.g. public transportation, water management).</p>
How it works

IREC prosumers can pool their resources and aggregate demand by participating in REC, allowing them to gain greater negotiating power with energy retailers and suppliers. This is one of the primary advantages of this BM. However, successful implementation requires agreement from all stakeholders, as well as technological and physical infrastructures capable of supporting and monitoring energy, financial, and information transactions for billing purposes.

The involvement of key partners — such as industrial park managers, resident businesses, local authorities, and financing bodies — is essential for tailoring and implementing effective BMs. Their inputs ensure that the proposed models: (i) address specific energy needs and challenges (ii) align with local socio-economic and regulatory contexts (iii) enhance long-term viability through stakeholder buy-in.

Reference project in operation for the BM3

Scientific references refer to as “community prosumerism” [20] or “top-down approach” [21]. Additionally, project deliverable D2.3 provides examples of public-private partnership. The ENERGIZE BM3 model aims to overcome common barriers such as mistrust, regulatory complexity, and imbalance resource allocation, fostering more inclusive and sustainable energy systems. BM3 propose IRECs as a framework for general project collaboration and a shared community-based approach.

3.4 BM4 – IREC for flexibility services

Table 3-4 BM4 description

BM4 in a nutshell
An IREC for flexibility services acts as a community aggregator, installing smart energy systems and renewables within a defined community. It provides comprehensive energy management platforms for all members. By aggregating member flexibility, the IREC enables participation in local energy markets, creating new revenue streams for members that accept demand-side managements or production flexibility actions (e.g. load shifting and peak shaving).
Overview
In BM4 IREC acts as flexibility aggregation, enabling small and medium enterprises to participate in energy markets by pooling their demand and production flexibility. Individual consumers often lack the resources and scale to meet market requirements, but aggregation addresses this barrier.
Community aggregators, operating either locally or at the power system level, contract with members to provide flexibility through changes in energy consumption patterns with direct or indirect control. These contracts may involve (i) dispatchable programs (e.g. direct load control) (ii)

non-dispatchable programs (e.g. dynamic pricing). Aggregators provide the necessary technology (smart meters, energy management systems, etc.) and manage the complexity of market participation. Members benefit from reduced energy bills and potential new revenue streams through flexibility trading. Aggregators profit from their role in market participation.

These "communities of interest" can be initiated by aggregators or end-users, with end-users actively involved in decision-making through contractual agreements. Successful aggregation depends on (i) robust ICT infrastructure, (ii) supportive regulatory frameworks, and (iii) effective alignment of interests among IREC members.

How it works

BM4 is implemented by an Industrial Park group that wants to offer energy flexibility by adjusting production schedules across different time horizons. BM4 consist of three key asset clusters: (i) renewable power generation plant, (ii) systems and labour for energy management and flexibility services and (iii) available load that could be shifted/adjusted. All the three asset clusters are owned and controlled by the same entity, who is also committed to operate them in a kind of integrated business.

Key partners include (i) industrial park members, (ii) technology providers (including renewable energy and smart meter suppliers) and (iii) national authorities, such as distribution system operators (DSOs) which facilitate local flexibility market or peer-to-peer trading between members.

Reference project in operation for the BM1

Scientific references classify this model as a "community flexibility aggregator" [20]. ENERGIZE BM4 can overcome key social barriers such as concerns over data privacy and trust, regulatory complexity and lack of knowledge about flexibility services and market participation.

3.5 BM5 – IREC mixed ownership and multi-services

Table 3-5 BM5 description

BM5 in a nutshell

A flexible, hybrid business model that combines elements of member ownership, ESCo partnership, and public/private investment. BM5 enables a multi-layered governance structure—where industries, service providers, and public actors jointly develop and operate renewable energy assets, storage, and smart grid services. It aims to maximize local value creation, scalability, and resilience, especially where full private or full public leadership may be infeasible.

Overview

BM5 is designed for industrial areas with diverse stakeholder profiles, where neither a fully member-owned model (BM1) nor an ESCo-led model (BM2) fits all needs. It emphasizes flexibility by distributing roles across stakeholders:

- Industries may co-own or lease renewable assets.
- ESCo may operate and maintain systems under performance-based contracts.
- Public entities may co-invest or facilitate regulatory alignment.

BM5 promotes modular development, allowing the community to gradually evolve from a basic REC to an advanced energy and flexibility hub. It's especially relevant in pilot zones where multi-sectoral coordination is required.

How it works

BM5 is governed by a joint operational committee representing all key stakeholders. Ownership and risk are shared proportionally. Revenue is generated from a mix of self-consumption, grid services, and third-party leases. Financing options include blended finance (grants, loans, ESCo contracts, and cooperative investment). The model is ideal for projects seeking scalability and resilience while avoiding over-reliance on a single actor.

Reference project in operation for the BM1

This model reflects evolving “community-platform” [20] and “multi-actor cooperative” [21] structures referenced in recent literature on industrial energy ecosystems and flexible REC configurations. It builds on practical lessons from energy hubs and sector-coupled pilots in Europe.

3.6 Preliminary business model canvas

In line with the goals of the ENERGIZE project, this section presents a comparative framework of preliminary BM canvas for IRECs. These models are designed to support the development and replication of cooperative energy solutions in selected pilot industrial parks, fostering clean energy production, demand-side flexibility, and stakeholder collaboration.

The presented models reflect different ownership, governance, and service configurations that are relevant across diverse regulatory and industrial settings. While they are informed by the technical and operational analysis carried out in the early stages of the project, they are explicitly defined as provisional and adaptable. The final design of each BM will evolve through participatory processes involving local stakeholders via workshops, online consultations, and bilateral engagements.

To ensure clarity and usability, the BMs are described using the Business Model Canvas (BMC) format [25], covering the nine standard blocks. This approach allows stakeholders and project partners to assess and compare the models along strategic and operational dimensions.

Table 3-6 BMC for IREC models

BM Canvas Block	BM1	BM2	BM3	BM4	BM5
1. Value Proposition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower energy costs • Control over assets • Carbon emission reduction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Turnkey energy solution • No upfront investment • Guaranteed performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social and territorial sustainability • Mayor local value impact • Empowerment of local stakeholder 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active market participation • Reduced regional grid stress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixed benefit partners • Blended economic and environmental returns
2. Customer Segments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial Park companies • Shared facility tenants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium-large energy consumers • Property owners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipalities, citizens, local businesses • Energy vulnerable groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DSOs/TSOs • Flexible users • Energy market operators • Aggregated industrial cluster 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixed group: firms, ESCo and public actors • Energy users with complementary profiles • Real estate and infrastructure managers
3. Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal committees • App and dashboard • Web/social channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commercial agreements • Dedicated customer service • Report and analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local events and public platforms • Community assemblies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation software's • Real-time energy platforms • Energy marketplace 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-stakeholder platform • Web, app and meeting
4. Customer Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participative management • Transparent cost sharing • Voting mechanism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodic reporting • Minimal user involvement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust based participatory • Higher user involvement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical engagement with market actors • Data driven personalisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared governance structures • Feedback loops • Hybrid relation based on roles
5. Revenue Streams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentive on shared self-consumption • Feed-in premiums 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy savings • Fixed fees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public grants • Voluntary contribution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexibility payment from grid operators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixed: energy sales service and grants

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Energy service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Optional leasing of equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Incentive of shared self-consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Capacity/reserve markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Mobility and storage service
6. Key Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •RES plants •Internal staff •Monitoring platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Financial capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Public assets and facilities •Community engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Digital control systems •Smart meters and sensors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Shared assets
7. Key Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Energy production •Monitoring and optimization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Reporting and compliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Community engagement •Educational activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Flexibility management •Demand forecasting •Communication with DSOs and market operator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Integration of generation, storage, flexibility •Energy balancing •Resource optimization
8. Key Partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Local industries •Energy consultant •DSOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Technology provider •Financial institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Municipalities •Cooperatives •NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •DSOs and aggregators •ICT and data providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Mixed: public, private, ESCo and financial actors •Universities
9. Cost Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Initial investment in RES •Maintenance and insurance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •O&M service fee •Licensing cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Community management cost •Awareness and facilitation costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •IT development and support •Advisory •Maintenance of automation systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Capital investments •Coordination and governance costs

This comparative table will serve as a strategic tool to:

- Support dialogue during stakeholder workshops.
- Identify barriers or enablers related to local conditions.
- Assist pilot leaders in selecting and tailoring the most suitable BM(s) for implementation.

The business models will be further refined during WP3 and WP5, incorporating stakeholders' inputs from national and regional contexts.

4 Key steps list mapping

4.1 Map rationale

To guide the structured development of Industrial Renewable Energy Communities (IRECs), a set of key steps has been identified and organised into a comprehensive mapping framework. This framework is built upon two core dimensions: **three sequential development phases** and **three thematic focus areas**.

The **development phases**—*Initial Definition, Setting-Up and Development, and Consolidation and Growth*—represent the chronological stages through which an IREC typically evolves. Running in parallel, the **thematic areas**—*Governance and Participation, Financing and Legal Aspects, and Energy and Technical Projects*—highlight the essential domains that must be addressed throughout each phase.

For every thematic area, the mapping outlines **specific actions** to be undertaken, along with the **key stakeholders** responsible for or affected by their implementation. These interlinked elements form the basis of the mind mapping approach developed in this task.

Overall, this mapping provides a structured, actionable, and replicable framework that supports the planning, implementation, and long-term success of IRECs. It is intended to serve as a practical tool for stakeholders aiming to establish or strengthen urban-industrial energy communities across Europe.

4.1.1 Phases

4.1.1.1 Phase 1: Initial Definition Phase

This phase lays the strategic and conceptual groundwork for the IREC. It focuses on identifying common values, establishing collaborative intent among stakeholders, and exploring feasibility. Key actions include facilitation, building a shared vision, defining the business model, conducting cost-benefit analyses, forming an initial legal entity, and leveraging local assets. This phase also integrates social responsibility and lays the foundation for trust and network building.

4.1.1.2 Phase 2: Setting-Up & Development Phase

This is the implementation phase where the IREC's governance, legal, financial, and technical infrastructure is established. Activities include forming a leadership team, signing foundational agreements, securing financing, integrating renewable energy and circularity solutions, and drafting participation rules. Special attention is paid to stakeholder alignment, long-term planning, and regulatory compliance. The goal is to operationalise the IREC with structured participation and viable energy systems.

4.1.1.3 Phase 3: Consolidation and Growth Phase

This phase ensures long-term sustainability and enables the IREC to evolve. The focus is on capacity building, stakeholder education, monitoring, and technological innovation. Communication becomes key—sharing success stories, engaging the wider community, and consolidating operations. Financial

resilience and the expansion of services (e.g., complementary solutions) are core goals to ensure replication and scaling.

4.1.2 Areas

4.1.2.1 Area 1: Governance and Participation

This domain refers to the social and organisational structures that support collaboration. It encompasses stakeholder engagement, leadership formation, decision-making mechanisms, facilitation, education, and community outreach. Effective governance ensures inclusiveness, transparency, and accountability, evolving from informal collaboration to institutionalised participation over time.

4.1.2.2 Area 2: Financing and Legal Aspects

This area includes all activities related to securing economic viability and legal standing. It involves defining business models, conducting cost-benefit assessments, creating legal entities, navigating regulations, and applying suitable financial mechanisms. As the project matures, it also aims to achieve economic sustainability and balance environmental and financial goals.

4.1.2.3 Area 3: Energy and Technical Projects

This technical domain covers the energy infrastructure and innovations that drive decarbonisation. It includes leveraging location advantages, integrating renewable and circular solutions, minimising environmental impact, and enabling scalability. In later phases, it also involves technological innovation, monitoring, and expanding into new energy services.

4.2 Key steps maps

Figure 4-1 Key Steps Map Areas to set-up an Industrial Renewable Energy Community

Figure 4-2 Key Steps Map to set-up an Industrial Renewable Energy Community

Figure 4-3 Detailed Initial Phase-Governance and participation

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Figure 4-4 Detailed Initial Phase- Financing and legal

Figure 4-5 Detailed Initial Phase-Energy and technical projects

Figure 4-6 Detailed Setting-up Phase- Governance and participation

Figure 4-7 Detailed Setting-up Phase- Financing and legal

Figure 4-8 Detailed Setting-up Phase - Energy and technical projects

Figure 4-9 Detailed Consolidation Phase- Governance and participation

Figure 4-10 Detailed Consolidation Phase- Financing and legal

Figure 4-11 Detailed Consolidation Phase - Energy and technical projects

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